

Non-viral Cell Penetrating Peptides for microRNA Delivery and Regulation of NP Cell Phenotype

Marcos N. Barcellona^{1,2}, Tara Ni Neill^{1,2}, Fergal J. O'Brien¹⁻³, James E. Dixon⁴, Caroline M. Curtin¹⁻³, Conor T. Buckley¹⁻³

¹Trinity Biomedical Sciences Institute (TBSI), Trinity College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland, ²Advanced Materials and Bioengineering Research (AMBER) Centre, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI) and TBSI, Dublin, Ireland, ³Tissue Engineering Research Group (TERG), RCSI, Dublin, Ireland, ⁴The University of Nottingham Biodiscovery Institute (BDI), Nottingham, U.K.

INTRODUCTION:

MicroRNAs (miRs) have emerged as a promising class of nucleic acids for different applications in the field of tissue engineering. Their small size (19-23 nucleotides) offers benefits in terms of transfection efficiencies, and their high specificity allows for reduced off-target effects (Baumann and Winkler 2014). In the current work we sought to employ non-viral vectors as miR delivery tools in order to modify matrix deposition rates in cells of the nucleus pulposus (NP). Specifically, we sought to validate the use of two cell penetrating peptides (CPPs), amphipathic peptide RALA and glycosaminoglycan (GAG)-binding enhanced transfection (GET) peptides. These were used as vectors to deliver miR-149-5p mimic and miR-221-3p-inhibitor, which were identified from the literature due to their relevance in modulating the disc microenvironment. Dual transfection with combined miRs was conducted to study the responses in aggrecan and type II collagen deposition, as well as MMP13 and ADAMTS5 expression.

METHODS:

Primary rat NP cells were obtained from caudal discs of adult Wistar rats (10-20 weeks). Following isolation, cells were cultured in normoxic conditions and expanded up to passage 3. We first surveyed the ability to form vector-miR nanocomplexes using polyethylenimine (PEI), RALA, chitosan, FLR, and FLR/FLH complexed with noncoding fluorescently tagged miR-Dy547. Lipofectamine was used as a positive transfection control. Internalization efficiency was quantified using flow cytometry on an LSRFortessa. Optimal N:P charge ratios were used based on previous works (Gonzalez-Fernandez et al. 2017, Dixon et al. 2016). The optimal dose of miR required to elicit functional responses was then studied by altering miR content without modifying the nanocomplexes' charge ratios. Prior to transfections, cells were cultured for 24 hours in serum free DMEM, and then challenged with 50 ng/mL TNF- α + 10 ng/mL IL-1 β . Transfections were then carried out by adding the miR-vector nanocomplexes to the cells and incubating at 37°C for 6 hours using the functional miR-149-5p-mimic and miR-221-3p-inhibitors. The supernatant was removed, and the cells were cultured according to the appropriate experimental setup. Cells were then fixed with 4% PFA and immunostained against aggrecan, type II collagen, MMP13, and ADAMTS5. Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad PRISM using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons tests.

RESULTS:

Our data suggests that RALA and FLR peptides yielded the highest internalization efficiencies while minimizing adverse cell effects (Fig. 1A, C). At miR concentrations of 10 ng/mL, a plateau in internalization efficiency was reached (Fig. 1B). In single miR transfections, we observed that RALA-miR-221-inhibitor promoted increases in deposition of both aggrecan and collagen type 2, while transfection with FLR-miR-149-mimic promoted nonsignificant trends towards decreased MMP13 and ADAMTS5 expression (data not shown). When employing a dual miR transfection using either RALA or FLR complexed with miR-221-inhibitor + miR-149-mimic, we observed significant decreases in expression of MMP13 and ADAMTS5, and increases in aggrecan and collagen 2 deposition (Fig. 1D). In addition to promoting a significant degree of cell death, the Lipofectamine control was observed to significantly increase ADAMTS5 expression (Fig. 1D). Neither the RALA- nor FLR-miR complexes exhibited this behavior, suggesting the vector-miR nanocomplexes may induce a lower degree of cell damage.

DISCUSSION:

Vector-miR nanocomplexes using both RALA and FLR vectors coupled with functional miRs 149-mimic and 221-inhibitor may be employed to modulate both pro-matrix deposition effects as well as to decrease the expression of matrix-degradation enzymes following inflammatory challenge. Nevertheless, while these approaches may effectively modulate specific behaviors, their effect on downstream pathway activation requires further exploration. The ability to employ vector-miR complexes in either a 3D cell micro-aggregate or in an organ culture model will allow for the study of functional outcomes in more translationally relevant systems.

SIGNIFICANCE:

Gene-based therapies are gaining traction due to their promising disease-modifying properties. As such, the use of non-viral vectors to deliver microRNA's in order to modulate expression of targets with a high degree of specificity may offer significant translational potential. Further characterization is required to better understand downstream or off-target effects, as well as to elucidate the mechanistic effects on pathway activation associated with gene delivery.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

This work was supported by the European Research Council (ERC-2019-CoG-864104; INTEGRATE).

REFERENCES:

- 1) Baumann and Winkler, "miRNA-based therapies: strategies and delivery platforms for oligonucleotide and non-oligonucleotide agents" *Future Med Chem*, 2014, 6 (17), 1967-1984.
- 2) Dixon et al., "Highly efficient delivery of functional cargoes by the synergistic effect of GAG binding motifs and cell-penetrating peptides" *PNAS*, 2016, 114 (20), E291-E299.
- 3) Gonzalez-Fernandez et al., "Mesenchymal stem cell fate following non-viral gene transfection strongly depends on the choice of delivery vector" *Acta Biomaterialia*, 2017, 55, 226-238.

Figure 1: A) Representative images of vector-miR-Dy547 transfection and internalization in rat NP cells and B) associated quantification. C) Cell viability effects of transfection vectors. D) Quantification of protein expression following cytokine challenge and subsequent vector-miR transfection using dual miR-221-3p-inhibitor and miR-149-5p-mimic.